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Argon plasma-modified bacterial nanocellulose: Cell-specific differences in the interaction with fibroblasts and endothelial cells

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ABSTRACT

Unique properties of bacterial nanocellulose (BNC), such as high purity, water retention, nanofibrillar structure and non-cytotoxicity, allow its application in regenerative medicine, particularly for active wound healing and for skin tissue engineering. However, its biological activity is not fully sufficient to be considered a good cell scaffold. This can be enhanced by physicochemical modifications, particularly plasma treatment. In this work, air-dried (AD) or lyophilized (L) BNC samples were modified in a direct current Ar⁺ plasma discharge (PM). BNC_AD samples showed higher surface roughness, tensile strength and Young's modulus but a lower swelling ratio than BNC_L samples. The swelling ratio of BNC_L samples further increased after PM. The samples were subjected to six-day *in vitro* cell culture tests with normal human dermal fibroblasts (NHDFs) or human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVECs), i.e. cell types important for skin defect healing. NHDFs adhered in higher numbers, by a larger cell spreading area and reached higher cell population densities on PM samples than on unmodified samples. However, in HUVECs, this effect of PM on cell growth was less pronounced or even opposite, especially on mechanically weaker and more swellable BNC_L. At the same time, both cell types preferred mechanically stronger BNC_AD for their adhesion and growth, which was more apparent in HUVECs. The expression of mRNA for markers of cell adhesion and phenotypic maturation in NHDFs (talin, vinculin, CD90) was generally similar on BNC_PM and on tissue culture polystyrene. In HUVECs, the expression of vinculin and PECAM-1 on all BNC samples was lower than on polystyrene, but the expression of KDR (VEGF receptor 2) was higher, especially on BNC_PM. These results indicate cell type-specific differences in the response to various BNC modifications, which must be properly balanced to accommodate various cell types needed for wound healing and skin tissue engineering.

1. Introduction

Bacterial nanocellulose (BNC) is a polysaccharide (linear polymer of glucose) produced by acetic bacteria on the interface between cultivation fluid and air. Although BNC is chemically identical to "ordinary" plant cellulose, it exhibits specific chemical and physical properties that make it promising for a wide range of industrial and biomedical applications (Dayal & Catchmark, 2016; Bacakova et al., 2019; Pogorelova et al., 2020; Yang et al., 2024). These properties include high purity (i.e. absence of byproducts like lignin, pectin, hemicelluloses, etc.), high water retention capacity (important for keeping moisture in skin

wounds and for removing the exudate), suitable mechanical properties mimicking those of soft tissues, mainly skin (i.e., high elasticity and conformability coupled with relatively high tensile strength), high crystallinity and particularly the micro- and nanofibrillar structure, which mimics the architecture of native extracellular matrix (ECM) in the human tissues (Torres et al., 2012; Kuzmenko et al., 2013; Bacakova et al., 2019; Osorio et al., 2019). Another important advantage of BNC is its non-toxicity, which is a crucial factor for its successful biomedical applications (Nosrati et al., 2021, 2023; Yang et al., 2024).

All these favorable properties of BNC can be further modulated by combination with other natural or synthetic polymers and compounds,

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such as collagen, gelatin, chitosan, pectin, alginate, poly(ϵ -caprolactone), polyethylene glycol or electroactive polypyrrole (Dayal & Catchmark, 2016; Bacakova et al., 2019; Nosrati et al., 2021; 2023). BNC has therefore been considered highly promising for use in the field of regenerative medicine, including tissue engineering and the construction of “intelligent” wound dressings. Dressings of this type are able to deliver various bioactive substances, such as cell adhesion-mediating proteins and oligopeptides, cytokines, growth factors, antimicrobial agents and particularly cells to wounds in order to promote their active healing (Bacakova et al., 2019; Pajorova et al., 2020; Nosrati et al., 2021, 2023).

The process of wound healing can be divided into four steps, namely hemostasis, inflammation, proliferation and remodelling (for a review, see Nosrati et al., 2021, 2023). An “intelligent” wound dressing can assist each of these four stages. In the phase of hemostasis, this dressing can capture molecules supporting cell adhesion, such as fibrin, fibronectin and vitronectin, or be itself a source of these molecules or adhesion oligopeptides derived from them. In the inflammation phase, this dressing can release cytokines, attracting cells of the immune system in order to prevent infection. A smart wound dressing can also primarily prevent this infection by releasing antimicrobial agents, such as antibiotics, metallic nanoparticles (Pogorelova et al., 2020; Nosrati et al., 2021; 2023) or plant-derived compounds (Chen et al., 2020; Zikmundova et al., 2020). In the proliferation phase, the dressing can release growth and angiogenic factors promoting the migration and growth of keratinocytes, fibroblasts and endothelial cells, or it can actively deliver these cell types to the wound. These cell types are then responsible for the ultimate remodelling of the wound site (Nosrati et al., 2021; 2023).

This study is mainly focused on the use of BNC as a carrier of cells promoting wound healing, especially its proliferative and remodeling phase, and possibly also as a scaffold for skin tissue engineering. However, it has been reported that BNC in its raw (i.e. pristine and unmodified) form does not promote sufficient cell adhesion because, as a glucose polymer, it lacks specific sites for binding by cell adhesion receptors (Torres et al., 2012; Kuzmenko et al., 2013; Bacakova et al., 2019; Osorio et al., 2019). It is therefore necessary to make the composition of BNC more like the ECM of mammalian cells. One way is to endow BNC with ligands for cell adhesion receptors, mostly oligopeptidic (Bacakova et al., 2011, 2019). However, commonly-used oligopeptides (e.g. RGD, IKVAV, KRSR), derived from cell adhesion-mediating proteins and immobilized on the surface of BNC, have not proved to be completely versatile, especially when only a single type of oligopeptide was used. The reason is that individual cell types preferentially recognize different oligopeptides for their adhesion and further functions (Fink et al., 2011; Pértile et al., 2012; Laboy-López et al., 2022). An alternative approach was to prepare a composite of BNC and a bioactive material. For example, composites of BNC with collagen (Kuzmenko et al., 2013), gelatin (Bao et al., 2022), albumin, fibronectin or heparin-chitosan (Wacker et al., 2021) enhanced the adhesion of vascular endothelial cells, smooth muscle cells or mesenchymal stem cells. Composites of BNC with collagen, apatite and osteogenic growth peptide supported the attachment, growth and osteogenic differentiation of bone-derived cells (Saska et al., 2017). However, these materials often have a relatively complicated composition and structure, and it is often challenging to prepare them in a well-defined and reproducible form. In addition, their preparation often requires the use of various catalytic, coupling or crosslinking agents (e.g. glutaraldehyde, Bao et al., 2022), which may act as cytotoxic for cells.

Another more versatile, simple and cost-effective method of material modification that improves cell adhesion and growth is plasma modification (PM). During PM, only the material surface is affected, while the bulk properties (elasticity, strength) remain unchanged. Using PM to alter the wettability, surface morphology and porosity, as well as the chemical composition, of a material creates materials with different swelling properties. The degree of PM of a material depends on the plasma parameters applied, for example, on the type of working gas

(Chu et al., 2002). Studies of BNC modification include employing N_2 , O_2 , CF_4 , and Ar plasma under various conditions. Using N_2 plasma, (Pertile et al., 2010) observed slightly decreased hydrophilicity, changes in surface chemistry and increased porosity. These plasma-modified BNC samples showed better N1E-115 neuroblast adhesion, as well as improved HMEC-1 endothelial cell adhesion and proliferation, but had no effect on 3T3 fibroblast adhesion. Kurniawan et al. (2012) used O_2 , N_2 and CF_4 plasma to modify BNC. These authors measured a decreased water contact angle for the N_2 and O_2 plasma-modified BNC samples, but an increased water contact angle for the CF_4 -modified samples. This resulted in enhanced I-929 fibroblast adhesion for the CF_4 samples, while the N_2 -modified and O_2 -modified samples only exhibited cell adhesion similar to that of the unmodified BNC. In our previous work (Kutová et al., 2021), we used Ar^+ plasma and observed morphological changes and higher porosity of BNC that resulted in increased HaCaT keratinocyte adhesion. It should be noted that the authors mentioned above used significantly different PM parameters, particularly in terms of working pressure, plasma power, and modification time.

However, BNC, which is harvested from the culture medium as a hydrogel-like never-dried cellulose, must be dried before subsequent PM. The choice of drying technique can significantly affect the morphology as well as the mechanical properties of a material, and this influences the adhesion and subsequent growth of the cells. While comparing the effects of oven drying and lyophilization, Illa et al. (2019) discovered that oven drying caused the BNC nanostructure to collapse, resulting in thinner and less porous samples but with higher tensile strength and a higher Young's modulus. However, the decreased porosity of oven-dried samples can subsequently lower the water absorption and, subsequently, lower the absorption of cell adhesion-mediating proteins. In accordance with this, in our earlier study, the initial adhesion of human epidermal HaCaT keratinocytes was supported better on BNC dried by lyophilization than on air-dried BNC with a collapsed nanostructure (Kutová et al., 2021). However, the relatively poor mechanical properties of lyophilized samples can also lead to insufficient cell adhesion (Bacakova et al., 2019). Therefore, further modifications of dried BNC are necessary to prepare a material with optimal properties for achieving sufficient cell attachment and growth. A promising way to preserve the BNC nanostructure and its porosity is crosslinking a never-dried BNC hydrogel with citric acid along with catalysts (Ciecholevska-Juško et al., 2021). One of the reaction products was the gas that ended up embedded in the BNC, preventing it from collapsing during oven drying. However, the introduction of other foreign chemical molecules into the BNC may negatively affect its subsequent colonization by cells (Ciecholevska-Juško et al., 2021; Koper et al., 2021; Flis et al., 2023). In the present study, we therefore focused on a simple physical modification of BNC, namely PM.

For a better understanding of the effect of PM on BNC, it is necessary to measure more combinations of PM parameters with the use of a particular drying technique in order to study its influence on cell behavior in deeper detail. It is only by exploring the impact of various approaches and parameters on the adhesion and growth of different cell types that a clearer picture will emerge that might provide the basis for a consistent methodology. We therefore investigated the adhesion, growth and phenotypic maturation of normal human dermal fibroblasts (NHDFs), i.e. a cell type important for reconstruction of the dermis, and also the behavior of human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVECs), i.e. a cell type necessary for vascularization of the regenerating tissue, on BNC samples dried either by air-drying or by lyophilization prior to subsequent Ar^+ PM.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials and chemicals

Bacterial cellulose (BNC) was prepared using *Komagataeibacter*

sacrofermentans bacterial strain (Leibniz Institut DSMZ, DSM 15,973, ATCC 700,178). The cultivation medium consisted of d-glucose (C₆H₁₂O₆, Penta), disodium hydrogen phosphate dodecahydrate (Na₂HPO₄•12H₂O, Lachema), special peptone (Oxoid), yeast extract (Oxoid), and citric acid monohydrate (C₆H₈O₇•H₂O, Penta). For purification after BNC harvesting sodium hydroxide (NaOH, Penta), sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS, C₁₂H₂₅NaO₄S, Sigma-Aldrich), and trypsin-EDTA solution (0.5 % w/w in saline solution, Sigma-Aldrich) were used. For air-drying, polytetrafluoroethylene foils was used (PTFE, Goodfellow). During Ar⁺ PM, an argon gas cylinder was used (purity 99.999 %, Siad). Phosphate buffered saline (PBS; NaCl, 8 g/L; KCl, 0.2 g/L; Na₂HPO₄•12H₂O, 2.85 g/L; KH₂PO₄, 0.2 g/L) with pH adjusted to 7.4 and Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium (DMEM; Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA; Cat. No. D5648) with 10 % of fetal bovine serum (FBS; Thermo Fisher Scientific, Gibco, Waltham, MA, USA; Cat. No. 10,270-106) were used to measure the swelling properties of prepared materials. The same medium, supplemented with µg/mL of gentamicin (Lek Pharmaceuticals, Ljubljana, Slovenia) was used for the cultivation of NHDFS (CLS Cell Lines Service, Eppelheim, Germany; Cat. No. 300,606). Another cell type used in this study was HUVECs (CLS Cell Lines Service, Eppelheim, Germany; Cat. No. 300,605), cultivated in Endothelial Cell Growth Medium 2 (EGM2), prepared from Endothelial Cell Basal Medium 2 (PromoCell GmbH, Heidelberg, Germany; Cat. No. C-22,111), supplemented with 1 % of antibiotic-antimycotic solution (v/v, Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA; Cat. No. A5955) and the growth medium-2 supplement pack (PromoCell, Heidelberg, Germany; Cat. No. C-39,211). Both cell types were cultured in 24-well tissue culture polystyrene plates (TPP, Trasadingen, Switzerland; Cat. No. 92,024). The cell viability was evaluated using the LIVE/DEAD viability/cytotoxicity kit for mammalian cells (Invitrogen, Molecular Probes; Cat. No. L3224), and the cell metabolic activity using resazurin (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA; Cat. No. R7017). For the real-time quantitative PCR (qPCR), Total RNA Purification Plus Micro Kit (Norgen Biotek, Thorold, ON, Canada; Cat. No. 48,500), Omniscript Reverse Transcription Kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany; Cat. No. 205,113), 5xHOT FIREPol Probe qPCR Mix Plus (ROX) (Solis BioDyne, Tartu, Estonia; Cat. No. 08-14-00,008) and TaqMan Gene Expression Assays (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA; Cat. No. 4,351,368) were applied.

2.2. Preparation of BNC foils

Bacterial nanocellulose was produced by *Komagataeibacter sacrofermentans* (Leibniz-Institut DSMZ, Braunschweig, Germany, DSM 15,973). Cultivation was carried out in 100 ml of Hestrin-Schramm (Hestrin & Schramm, 1954) culture medium consisting of d-glucose (20 g/L), disodium hydrogen phosphate dodecahydrate (6.8 g/L), special peptone (5 g/L), yeast extract (5 g/L), and citric acid monohydrate (1.3 g/L), pH 5.8. Cultivation lasted for at least 21 days at 28 °C in a 250 ml Erlenmeyer flask under static conditions. Purification of nanocellulose from bacteria and from the medium residue was performed by rinsing twice in boiling 0.1 M NaOH, and then by rinsing at least twice in boiling distilled water for at least 10 min until clean. In order to fully remove the bacteria residues, the samples were washed in a 10 % (m/m) solution of sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) for 20 min and trypsin solution at 37 °C for 10 min. The washed BNC hydrogels were solidified via air-drying (AD) on polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) foil at room temperature (20 °C) and atmospheric pressure overnight (i.e., for 20 h), or by lyophilization (L). The lyophilization process took place on an Alpha 3-4 LSCbasic freeze dryer (Christ, Osterode am Harz, Germany) for at least 24 h. The condenser temperature was set to -105 °C and the pressure to 0.07 mBar. The BNC foils were solidified for at least 24 h prior at -80 °C. From the obtained solidified BNC foils weighing approx. 22 mg, either AD or L, circular samples with a diameter of 16 mm weighing roughly 0.8–1.4 mg were cut.

2.3. Plasma-modification of BNC foils

Ar⁺ plasma was employed to alter BNC foils' surface properties while preserving the bulk properties (Chu et al., 2002). During this process, the material surface is etched which leads to weight loss and increased roughness. Furthermore, ring-opening reactions can randomly occur with the simultaneous formation of highly active radicals. These radicals can bind the atmospheric oxygen and form new functional groups (Kolarova et al., 2013). This can lead to changes in swelling properties and surface chemistry that can significantly affect the cell growth on the BNC foils.

The surface of the solid samples was modified in a direct current (glow, diode) Ar⁺ plasma discharge on a Balzers SCD 050 device (BAL-TEC, Balzers, Lichtenstein). The conditions were set as follows: gas purity of 99.997 %, Ar pressure of 7 Pa, electrode distance of 55 mm, electrode area of 48 cm², chamber volume of approx. 1 dm³, plasma volume of 0.24 dm³, electrical current of 12 mA, and voltage of 750 V. The samples were modified from both sides for 240 s.

2.4. Methods of analysis

The surface morphology of BNC was examined by atomic force microscopy (AFM) using a Dimension ICON microscope (Bruker, Billerica, MA, USA). Peak force quantitative nanomechanical measurement mode was employed with an Si ScanAsyst probe with 70 kHz resonance frequency and 0.4 N·m⁻¹ spring constant. Images 3 × 3 µm² in area with 512 × 512 resolution were obtained at a 1 Hz scanning rate. NanoScope Analysis software (version 1.80, Bruker Corp., Billerica, MA, USA) was used for data processing. The surface area difference (SAD), the arithmetic mean roughness and the root mean square roughness were calculated from the displayed images.

The swelling ratios (SR) of the BNC samples were calculated from tests performed in distilled water, phosphate-buffered saline (PBS), and Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium with fetal bovine serum (DMEM + FBS, see above). Weighed samples were immersed into the liquid for a specified time (from 1 min to 1 week). After this time, the samples were removed from the liquid, were left in a vertical position to drip for 30 s and were weighed again. The SR was calculated using the equation: SR = ((m₁ - m₀)/m₀) · 100 %, where m₀, m₁ stand for weight before and after immersion, respectively (Slepičková Kasálková et al., 2020). Six measurements were performed for each experimental group of BNC samples.

Tensile mechanical properties were measured using an Instron Universal Testing Machine, Model 3365 (Instron, Norwood, MA, USA) according to ISO 37. The dumbbell-shaped samples with the working part 10 mm long and 5 mm wide were cut from dried BNC_AD and BNC_L foils. The thickness of the samples was measured with a QuantuMike IP65 digital caliper micrometer (0–25 mm, 0.001 mm, Mitutoyo, Kawasaki, Japan). The samples were stretched by 10 mm/min until they fractured. The mechanical properties were calculated from the stress-strain curve, which was plotted by Bluehill software: the tensile strength and tensile strain from the fraction moment as the maximum stress and elongation, respectively, the Young's modulus from the slope of the linear part of the curve. Ten measurements were performed for each experimental group of BNC samples.

The water contact angles of the BNC samples were measured by the sessile drop method to evaluate the changes in surface hydrophilicity by a DSA100 fully automated goniometer (KRÜSS GmbH, Hamburg, Germany). Drops of (2.0 ± 0.2) µl of water were deposited on the tested samples, and images were then taken after a 2 s delay. The contact angle was calculated from the captured image using the height/width method. Ten measurements were performed for each experimental group of BNC samples.

2.5. Cell cultivation

Normal human dermal fibroblasts (NHDFs), purchased from CLS Cell Lines Service (Eppelheim, Germany; Cat. No. 300,606) were cultivated in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium (DMEM; Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA; Cat. No. D5648) with 10 % of fetal bovine serum (FBS; Thermo Fisher Scientific, Gibco, Waltham, MA, USA; Cat. No. 10,270-106) and 40 µg/mL of gentamicin (Lek Pharmaceuticals, Ljubljana, Slovenia).

Human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVECs) purchased from CLS Cell Lines Service (Eppelheim, Germany; Cat. No. 300,605) were cultivated in Endothelial Cell Growth Medium 2 (EGM2), which was prepared from Endothelial Cell Basal Medium 2 (PromoCell GmbH, Heidelberg, Germany; Cat. No. C-22,111), supplemented with 1 % of antibiotic-antimycotic solution (v/v, Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA; Cat. No. A5955) and the growth medium-2 supplement pack (PromoCell, Heidelberg, Germany; Cat. No. C-39,211) containing hydrocortisone, heparin, ascorbic acid, epidermal growth factor (EGF), vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF), insulin-like growth factor-1 (IGF-1), fibroblast growth factor-2 (FGF-2) and 2 % of FBS.

The BNC membranes were sterilized in an autoclave (Tuttnauer, Breda, Netherlands; 121 °C, 23 min, 101.3 kPa) and were inserted in 24-well tissue culture polystyrene plates (TPP, Trasadingen, Switzerland; Cat. No. 92,024). The cells were seeded on BNC membranes at a density of approximately 16,000 cells/cm² (i.e., 30,000 cells/well). The volume of the cell culture medium was 1.5 mL/well. The cells were cultivated at 37 °C and in a humidified air atmosphere with 5 % CO₂. Pure tissue culture polystyrene wells were used as control samples.

2.6. Evaluation of the cell number, viability, cell spreading area and circularity

Cells on the BNC membranes were cultivated for 1, 3 and 6 days. Three samples were used for each experimental group and time interval, and the experiments were repeated three times. On days 1, 3 and 6 after seeding, the cells on the samples were stained by the LIVE/DEAD viability/cytotoxicity kit for mammalian cells (Invitrogen, Molecular Probes; Cat. No. L3224) according to the manufacturer's protocol (<https://www.thermofisher.com/order/catalog/product/L3224>). The cells were incubated with two probes detecting the esterase activity in living cells (2 µM calcein AM producing green fluorescence), and the other indicating the membrane damage in dead cells (4 µM ethidium homodimer-1 emitting red fluorescence) for 5 min at 37 °C in a humidified air atmosphere containing 5 % of CO₂. For each sample, pictures of randomly selected fields homogeneously distributed on the surface of the sample were taken under an Olympus IX 51 epifluorescence microscope (obj. 4x) equipped with a DP 70 digital camera. Live and dead cells distinguished by the green and red fluorescence were then manually counted in these microphotographs. On days 1 and 3 after seeding, 8 to 34 measurements of cell number and cell viability were performed for each experimental group of samples, cell type and time interval. The size of the cell spreading area and the cell circularity were measured on day 1 after seeding using ImageJ software (National Institutes of Health, Bethesda, Maryland, USA) after identifying the cells by thresholding. Both of these parameters were measured in 273–1309 cells for each experimental group of samples and cell type.

2.7. Evaluation of cell metabolic activity by the resazurin test

The cell metabolic activity, which is an indicator of cell number and viability, was estimated on day 6 after seeding using a resazurin assay, based on the activity of mitochondrial dehydrogenases. Each sample was incubated in 1 ml of a fresh culture medium (corresponding to the given cell type) with resazurin (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA; Cat. No. R7017) at a final concentration of 40 mM for 2 h at 37 °C in a humidified air atmosphere containing 5 % CO₂. Wells without cells were

used as blanks for each combination of media with the resazurin solution. The fluorescence of the final metabolite resorufin was measured (Ex/Em = 530/590 nm) in 150 µl per well in a 96-well plate by a Synergy HT Multi-Mode Microplate reader (BioTek, Winooski, VT, USA) after 2 h of incubation. Three measurements were performed for each experimental group of samples and cell type.

2.8. Gene expression of cell adhesion and differentiation markers

The expression of genes, encoding markers of cell adhesion and differentiation (i.e. phenotypic maturation), was analyzed at mRNA level using real-time quantitative PCR (qPCR) on day 6 after seeding. The selected genes of interest included:

TLN1 and *VCL* (genes encoding talin-1 and vinculin, respectively, i.e. focal adhesion proteins associated with cell adhesion receptors); *THY1* (gene for cluster of differentiation 90, i.e. CD90, used as a marker of fibroblasts); *PECAM1* (gene for platelet endothelial cell adhesion molecule-1, also known as CD31), and *KDR* (gene for vascular endothelial growth factor receptor 2, i.e. VEGFR2). Beta-2-microglobulin (*B2M*) was used as a reference (i.e. "housekeeping") gene.

Total RNA isolation was performed using a Total RNA Purification Plus Micro Kit (Norgen Biotek, Thorold, ON, Canada; Cat. No. 48,500) according to the manufacturer's protocol (available at <https://norgenbiotek.com/product/total-rna-purification-plus-micro-kit>). The RNA purity and concentration were evaluated by a Nano-Drop One Spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) from measurements of absorbance at 260 nm and 280 nm. Reverse transcription was performed using an Omniscript Reverse Transcription Kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany; Cat. No. 205,113) according to the manufacturer's protocol (available at <https://www.qiagen.com/us/resources/resource-detail?id=18c6457d-37c3-4116-82c8-c42ab935c1c9&lang=en>), with the use of Random Primer Mix (New England Biolabs, Ipswich, MA, USA; Cat. No. S1330S). The reaction ran in a T-Personal Thermocycler (Biometra, Göttingen, Germany). The real-time qPCR was performed using 5xHOT FIREPol Probe qPCR Mix Plus (ROX) (Solis BioDyne, Tartu, Estonia; Cat. No. 08-14-00,008) and TaqMan Gene Expression Assays (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA; Cat. No. 4,351,368) labeled with a fluorescein amidite (FAM) reporter dye specific to the following target human genes: *TLN1* (Hs00196775_m1), *VCL* (Hs00419715_m1), *THY1* (Hs00174816_m1), *PECAM1* (Hs01062579_m1), *KDR* (Hs00911700_m1), and a reference *B2M* gene (Hs00187842_m1). Real-time qPCR was carried out in a final reaction volume of 20 µl per well in a 96-well optical reaction plate using the LightCycler 480 Instrument (Roche, Basel, Switzerland). The parameters of the cycle were: 2 min at 50 °C, 10 min at 95 °C, 40 cycles of 15 s at 95 °C and 1 min at 60 °C. The relative gene expression levels were calculated as $-\Delta\Delta Ct$.

2.9. Statistical evaluation

Quantitative data were presented as the arithmetic mean \pm standard deviation (S.D.), the arithmetic mean \pm standard error of the mean (S.E. M.) or as median, quartiles and the interquartile range from 3 to 1309 measurements, depending on the type of experimental analysis. Statistical significance was evaluated using One-Way ANOVA, the Student–Newman–Keuls method, or using non-parametric Kruskal–Wallis One Way Analysis of Variance on Ranks, Dunn's method. Values of $p \leq 0.05$ were considered significant. PCR data was evaluated using One-Way ANOVA, the Holm–Sidak method. For these data, only values of $p < 0.01$ were considered significant. The data were normalized according to the gene expression in the cells grown on the bottom of standard polystyrene cultivation wells (calibrator; value set to zero in the graphs).

Fig. 1. Surface morphology of BNC_AD (A) and BNC_L (B), analyzed by AFM. The scanning areas were $3 \times 3 \mu\text{m}^2$ for both images with resolution 512×512 .

Table 1

Surface area difference (SAD), arithmetic mean roughness (R_a), and root mean square roughness (R_q) obtained from AFM micrographs.

Sample	SAD (%)	R_a (nm)	R_q (nm)
BNC_AD	24.3	31.0	38.6
BNC_L	15.4	15.4	21.4

All statistical analyses were performed using SigmaStat 4.0 (Systat Software Inc., USA). Graphs were created in GraphPad Prism 9 (GraphPad Software, USA).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Surface morphology of BNC

The surface morphology of BNC studied via AFM revealed the differences between BNC modified by air-drying (BNC_AD) or by lyophilization (BNC_L) before plasma modification (PM) (Fig. 1). Apart from Illa et al. (2019), few other scientists have studied the differences between various BNC drying methods (Chen et al., 2020; Zeng et al., 2014). Overall, these studies have shown that lyophilization maintains the nanostructure of never-dried hydrogels, leading to a material with higher porosity and a larger specific surface area, decreased crystallinity, and thicker fibers. In contrast, free hydroxyl groups forming hydrogen bonds lead to more folded polymer chains during air-drying. This phenomenon cannot occur when the polymer chain is frozen during the lyophilization process. Our results confirmed these assumptions.

As the morphology of the BNC_AD collapsed, it formed thinner pellicles with the fibers folded vertically to the BNC surface. This leads to a higher SAD (i.e., the percentage ratio between the surface area of the sample and its two-dimensional footprint) as well as to almost twice the surface arithmetic mean roughness (R_a) of BNC_AD (Table 1) compared to BNC_L, where the fibers are smoothed on the surface. However, due to the nanofibrillar structure of the samples, these values are not theoretically correct, since the AFM tip provides information only on the top layer of the porous structure. Nevertheless, this analysis can serve for a comparison of the samples and for a closer understanding of the cellular behavior on the material surface, given that this is how the cells will perceive the surface. Both BNC_AD and BNC_L displayed nanoscale R_a (i.e. less than 100 nm), which is considered beneficial for cell adhesion and growth due to the similarity of this parameter with the nanoarchitecture of the native ECM and the cell cytoplasmic membrane (for a review, see Bacakova et al., 2011). Unfortunately, it was impossible to measure the PM samples by AFM, probably due to a high static electric charge in the material and the enhanced surface porosity that we revealed in our previous work (Kutová et al., 2021).

Table 2

Mechanical properties of BNC samples measured using an Instron Universal Testing Machine. Mean \pm S.D. from 10 measurements.

Sample	Tensile strength (MPa)	Tensile strain (%)	Young's modulus (MPa)
BNC_AD	21.24 ± 11.03	8.44 ± 2.74	241 ± 102
BNC_L	4.63 ± 1.14	8.43 ± 1.86	53 ± 13
Rehydrated BNC_AD	31.31 ± 13.97	22.26 ± 5.69	135 ± 35
Rehydrated BNC_L	7.96 ± 2.52	21.20 ± 3.15	40 ± 13

3.2. Mechanical properties

Mechanical properties are often overlooked in connection with the issue of cell-substrate adhesion and further cell growth; however, they play an important role in the preparation of a satisfactory cell scaffold. Rigid matrices have usually been preferred to soft ones, because they provide firmer support for cells (Bacakova et al., 2011). We measured the tensile strength, strain and Young's modulus on BNC_AD and BNC_L samples either in a dry state or rehydrated for one hour in water to better mimic the behavior of the samples in a physiological environment in the subsequent *in vitro* tests with cells (Table 2). The AD samples showed almost 5 times higher tensile strength and Young's modulus. This could be attributed to the collapsed nanostructure of the AD samples, which leads to a higher concentration of hydrogen bonds strengthening the whole structure. However, the tensile strain was basically the same for both of the drying methods. For the AD samples, we obtained similar values to Pogorelova et al. (2020), who tested BNC under comparable conditions. The relatively high deviation of the values obtained for the AD samples could be attributed to inhomogeneity of the prepared samples, due to the basic characteristics of the materials originating from bacterial production. This can influence the measured thickness of the sample, which leads to inconsistent values of the mechanical properties calculated for the thickness of the material. The BNC_L samples are exempt from this, since the internal structure of the material is maintained. The thickness measurement error is therefore much lower for the BNC_L samples. Nevertheless, the values obtained for the mechanical properties are significantly different for the BNC_AD and BNC_L samples.

Illa et al. (2019) also compared two methods of drying (oven drying and lyophilization) and two different BNC-producing bacterial strains. These authors also found that the lyophilized samples showed decreased tensile strength and a lower Young's modulus. However, their oven-dried samples had a much higher Young's modulus and a lower tensile strain compared to the air-dried samples in our present work. This can be attributed to the increased temperature of drying, which can lead to even more pronounced folding of the cellulose nanofibers and to a much tougher and more rigid structure. Zeng et al. (2014) also investigated the different mechanical properties of air-dried and lyophilized samples. Their samples showed similar values of the

Fig. 2. Swelling ratios of BNC_AD (solid) and BNC_L (striped) in different liquids in the course of a week. Mean \pm S.D. from 6 measurements.

Fig. 3. Swelling ratio after 1-hour immersion in PBS of unmodified samples and samples 1 hour and 1 week after PM. Mean \pm S.D. from 6 measurements.

mechanical properties. However, it is important to note they used a different measurement method (a nanoindenter).

3.3. Swelling properties

Bacterial nanocellulose is capable of absorbing large amounts of water. To predict its behavior in tests *in vitro* and in subsequent usage, it is important to know its swelling properties in different liquids (Slepícková Kasálková et al., 2020). For the unmodified BNC_AD and BNC_L samples, we examined the swelling ratio (SR) in water, PBS and DMEM + FBS for a period of one week to obtain the maximum swelling capacity of the materials (Fig. 2). We observed a much higher SR for the BNC_L samples than for the BNC_AD samples. This is caused by the maintained nanostructure of the BNC_L samples with greater porosity, which leads to a larger amount of liquid absorbed into the bulk of the material. The higher presence of absorbed water, confirmed by Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), performed on BNC samples in our previous study (Kutová et al., 2021), can enhance the swelling ratio of BNC_L. We obtained similar SR for all liquids for the

BNC_AD samples. However, for the BNC_L samples, we observed that the SR of water and PBS was almost twice as high as the SR of DMEM + FBS. This could be due to the presence of relatively large molecules (proteins, peptides, vitamins, etc.) in the cultivation medium that clog the pores of the lyophilized material.

The changes in SR after plasma modification have been reported extensively (Kolarova et al., 2013; Slepícková Kasálková et al., 2020). However, to the best of our knowledge, BNC has not yet been described in this way. Based on the results for pristine material, we chose 1-hour immersion as a sufficient time to obtain the equilibrium value of the SR in PBS. To evaluate the longevity of the PM effect, we measured the SR 1 hour and 1 week after the PM of the samples (Fig. 3). We observed an increase in SR for the lyophilized PM samples. This is likely caused by the maintained nanostructure of these samples, which leads to a more porous material. On the one hand, the SR values for lyophilized samples after 1 h and for the aged samples after 1 week are comparable within the error of the measurement, which indicates the stability of the prepared PM samples. On the other hand, the BNC_AD showed a small and statistically irrelevant increase in the SR. This result corresponds with

Table 3

The contact angle of unmodified and aged BNC_AD samples. Mean \pm S. D. from 10 measurements.

Duration	Contact angle (°)
Unmodified	63.91 \pm 2.69 Kutová et al. (2021)
1 h	43.67 \pm 5.13
2 h	40.89 \pm 4.46
4 h	62.33 \pm 4.69
1 day	74.20 \pm 3.30
1 week	73.95 \pm 6.45
2 weeks	56.80 \pm 6.11
4 weeks	64.16 \pm 3.60

the XPS result that we obtained in our previous work ([Kutová et al., 2021](#)). There, we studied the O/C ratio that correlates with the presence of the hydroxyl groups on the material surface, which can influence its interactions with liquids. This ratio almost doubled for the lyophilized samples (0.6595 resp. 1.0125), but was almost the same for the air-dried samples (0.6124 resp. 0.6809).

3.4. Ageing of PM

It is well known ([Bhat & Upadhyay, 2002](#); [Kvítek et al., 2019](#); [Švorčík et al., 2006](#)) that the sample surface properties can change over time after PM. This can be attributed to the formation of reactive radicals that can bind the atmospheric humidity and form polar groups. Over time,

the polymer chains on the surface rearrange themselves, which leads to changes in the surface polarity. This can be illustrated via water contact angle measurements.

To better understand the behavior of samples in subsequent *in vitro* tests and to prove their stability, we studied the contact angle of aged samples. BNC_AD samples were plasma-modified and the contact angles were measured after a particular duration ([Table 3](#)). Immediately after PM, the contact angle dropped due to a higher concentration of surface polar groups. However, after 4 h, the contact angle increased again to values comparable with the contact angle of the unmodified sample. The contact angle value then remained stable for 4 weeks. Unfortunately, the contact angles of the lyophilized samples could not be measured because the liquid instantly soaked into the material.

3.5. Cell number, viability and morphology

On day 1 after seeding, the number of initially adhering viable human dermal fibroblasts (NHDFs) was similar or even higher on the BNC samples in comparison with the control polystyrene (PS) culture wells. These cells preferred plasma-modified BNC (BNC_PM) to unmodified BNC. The highest cell population density was found on BNC_AD_PM (median approx. 4800 cells/cm²), and was significantly higher in comparison with the cell number on BNC_L unmodified with plasma (median 3100 cells/cm²) and on control PS (median 3600 cells/cm²; [Fig. 4A](#)). The viability of the NHDFs, i.e. the percentage of viable cells in the population, on the BNC samples was comparable to the value

Fig. 4. The number (A, C) and the viability (B, D) of normal human dermal fibroblasts (NHDFs; A, B) and human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVECs; C, D) on day 1 after seeding in the control polystyrene (PS) wells or on BNC samples (AD: air-dried, AD_PM: air-dried plasma-modified, L: lyophilized, L_PM: lyophilized plasma-modified). Kruskal–Wallis One Way Analysis of Variance on Ranks, Dunn’s method. The box plot black central line shows the median; its outer edges represent the 1st and 3rd quartile (Q1 is the 25th percentile, Q3 is the 75th percentile of the sample), the whiskers depict the maximum and minimum values. Statistically significant differences among the experimental groups ($p \leq 0.05$) are indicated above the columns by Roman numerals of the differing groups. For each experimental group of samples and for each parameter, 19–34 measurements for NHDFs and 16–22 measurements for HUVECs were performed.

Fig. 5. Morphology of normal human dermal fibroblasts (NHDFs) and human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVECs) on day 1 after seeding on BNC samples (AD: air-dried, AD_PM: air-dried plasma-modified, L: lyophilized, L_PM: lyophilized plasma-modified), and in the control polystyrene (PS) wells. The cells were stained with a LIVE/DEAD kit. Viable cells are colored green, dead cells are red. Olympus IX 51 epifluorescence microscope, DP 70 digital camera, objective 4 ×, eyepiece 10 × (total magnification of the optical system 40 ×), scale bar 200 μm.

on the control PS, with the exception of BNC_AD, where the cell viability was significantly lower (median 91 %) in comparison with BNC_L_PM (median 95 %) and the control PS (median 100 %; Fig. 4B).

HUVECs generally adhered in higher initial numbers (median from 7600 to 13,900 cells/cm²) than NHDFs (median from 3100 to 4800 cells/cm²). However, the number of HUVECs was significantly lower on all tested BNC samples in comparison with the value on the control PS (median 13,700 cells/cm²), with the exception of BNC_L unmodified with plasma (median 10,700 cells/cm²). The lowest cell number was detected on unmodified BNC_AD (median 7300 cells/cm²; Fig. 4C). The cell viability of HUVECs on BNC samples, with the exception of BNC_L, was significantly lower than on PS (median 98 %). However, it was still relatively high, ranging between 86–95 %. These relatively high values of cell viability are indicative of the non-cytotoxicity of the material

according to ISO standard No. 10,993–5, where only a decrease in cell viability below 70 % can be considered biologically relevant and indicative of cytotoxicity of the material (Ciecholevska-Juško et al., 2021). The highest percentage of viable cells was detected in cultures on BNC_L and the lowest percentage on BNC_AD (Fig. 4D).

Microscopic images of the cells are presented in Fig. 5. It is apparent that the NHDFs are distributed less homogeneously on BNC_PM than on unmodified BNC and on PS, i.e. they show a tendency to form clusters. However, as indicated by Fig. 6A, the size of the cell spreading area, i.e. the cell-material projected area, is larger on BNC_PM samples (median 720–900 μm²) than on plasma-unmodified BNC (median 430–540 μm²), although the cell spreading area on all tested BNC samples was significantly smaller than on the control PS (median 1820 μm²). The circularity of NHDF showed an opposite trend. This parameter was significantly

Fig. 6. The size of the cell spreading area (A, C) and the circularity (B, D) of normal human dermal fibroblasts (NHDFs; A, B) and human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVECs; C, D) on day 1 after seeding on the BNC samples (AD: air-dried, AD_PM: air-dried plasma-modified, L: lyophilized, L_PM: lyophilized plasma-modified). Cells were stained with a LIVE/DEAD kit, and the cell spreading area and circularity were evaluated using ImageJ software. Kruskal–Wallis One Way Analysis of Variance on Ranks, Dunn’s method. The data distribution is visualized as violin plots, where the dashed central line shows the median, the lower and upper fine dashed lines represent the 1st and 3rd quartile (Q1 is the 25th percentile, Q3 is the 75th percentile of the sample), and the bottom and top edge of the plot depict the maximum and minimum values. Statistically significant differences among the experimental groups ($p \leq 0.05$) are indicated above the columns by Roman numerals of the differing groups (all: significantly different in comparison with all other groups). For each experimental group of samples, each parameter was measured in 273–1186 cells for NHDFs and in 308–1309 cells for HUVECs.

higher in cells cultured on all tested BNC samples than in cells on the control PS. At the same time, the cell circularity was significantly lower on BNC_AD_PM than on the other tested BNC samples (Fig. 6B).

Microscopic images (Fig. 5) further show that in HUVECs, BNC_AD_PM increased the amount of initially adhered cells and their spreading area in comparison with BNC_AD, but on BNC_L, the cell spreading area appears larger than on BNC_L_PM. These observations were confirmed by measuring the size of the cell spreading area. This area reached the largest size on plasma-unmodified BNC_L (median $1290 \mu\text{m}^2$), and significantly exceeded (almost three times) the values on the other types of BNC (median 440 – $470 \mu\text{m}^2$), and also on the control PS (median $990 \mu\text{m}^2$; Fig. 6C). The lowest circularity of HUVECs was observed in cells cultured on unmodified BNC_L and on the control PS, i. e. on materials with the largest cell spreading area. The highest cell circularity was obtained in HUVEC cultured on BNC_AD and BNC_L_PM, i. e. on substrates with the lowest cell spreading area (Fig. 6D).

Proper attachment and spreading of anchorage-dependent cells are prerequisites for their subsequent proliferation, for good colonization of a biomaterial scaffold with cells, and for proper formation of a tissue replacement. A polygonal or spindle-like cell shape and a large cell spreading area are factors indicating a good cell-material interaction,

while high cell circularity is usually a sign of weak cell-material contact and of the inability of the cells to spread adequately on the material (Filova et al., 2017; Steinerova et al., 2021).

Taken together, in NHDFs, PM clearly supported initial cell attachment, viability and spreading on both BNC_AD and BNC_L, while in HUVECs, the PM had no effect or even a negative effect. On the one hand, PM can modulate the polarity and wettability of the material surface to appropriate values needed for stable adsorption of sufficient amounts of cell adhesion-mediating molecules from the culture medium, e.g. fibronectin and vitronectin, which are bound by cell adhesion receptors (e.g. integrins) through bioactive sites in these molecules, e.g. specific amino acid sequences like RGD, REDV, IKVAV etc. (Kurniawan et al., 2012; for a review, see Bacakova et al., 2011). In addition, PM can increase the porosity of lyophilized BNC, which facilitates cell penetration inside the scaffolds (Pertile et al., 2010). On the other hand, increased porosity can enhance the material swelling (Figs. 2, 3). This can lead to further softening of the material, especially of BNC_L, which was relatively soft even before PM (Table 2). BNC_L_PM could then no longer provide sufficiently firm support for cell spreading, although the number of initially attached HUVECs was even slightly higher on BNC_L than on BNC_AD (Fig. 4C). This higher cell number can be attributed to the fact that highly porous BNC_L provides a larger space for cell attachment. Similarly, a higher number of initially attached cells was observed in human HaCaT keratinocytes on BNC_L in our earlier study (Kutová et al., 2021).

On day 3 after seeding, NHDFs continued to prefer BNC_PM for their growth, which was apparent especially on BNC_L_PM. On this sample, the cell number (median $44,800 \text{ cells/cm}^2$) was comparable with the value on the control PS (median $39,400 \text{ cells/cm}^2$), and was approx. five times higher than on unmodified BNC_L (median 8100 cells/cm^2). Similarly, the cell number on BNC_AD_PM (median $22,200 \text{ cells/cm}^2$) was almost twice as high as on plasma-untreated BNC_AD (median $11,900 \text{ cells/cm}^2$). The viability of the NHDFs was high on all tested BNC samples, ranging between approx. 95–98% with the lowest viability on BNC_AD and BNC_L (Fig. 7A, B).

However, in HUVECs, there was no significant difference in cell numbers on unmodified and PM samples, and these cells clearly preferred BNC_AD to BNC_L for their growth. The cell numbers on both BNC_AD (median $61,600 \text{ cells/cm}^2$) and BNC_AD_PM (median $57,800 \text{ cells/cm}^2$) were almost three times as high as on both BNC_L (median $22,200 \text{ cells/cm}^2$) and BNC_L_PM (median $19,300 \text{ cells/cm}^2$), and were rather comparable to the value on PS (median $75,100 \text{ cells/cm}^2$). This could be due to the stronger mechanical properties of BNC_AD, which provided firmer support than BNC_L for cell growth. Moreover, the viability of HUVECs on the BNC_L_PM samples was only approx. 75%, while on the remaining BNC samples, the viability reached more than 90% (Fig. 7C, D).

The different behavior of HUVECs and NHDFs on BNC_AD and BNC_L can be explained by the fact that endothelial cells are polarized cobblestone-like cells designated to cover the inner surface of blood vessels, i. e. to form 2D-like monolayers, while fibroblasts are non-polarized spindle-shaped mesenchymal cells, readily penetrating porous scaffolds and growing in 3D environments. A cell type-specific behavior was also observed on plasma-modified lyophilized BNC scaffolds in a study by Pertile et al. (2010) although, in that study, plasma modification improved the adhesion and growth of endothelial cells, while the behaviour of fibroblasts was unchanged. This disproportion between that study and our work could be explained by the fact that we studied the cell adhesion and growth only on the surface of BNC, from where the cells could be delivered to the wound if BNC was used as a wound dressing. In contrast, Pertile et al. (2010) also considered the ingrowth of endothelial cells into the interior of the porous material, which is necessary for pre-vascularization of the tissue-engineered construct. The ability of endothelial cells to migrate vertically into BNC pellicles was also shown in a study by Berti et al. (2013).

Migration of endothelial and other cell types into the porous BNC,

Fig. 7. Number and viability of normal human dermal fibroblasts (NHDFs; **A, B**) and human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVECs; **C, D**) on day 3 after seeding on the control polystyrene (PS) wells or on BNC samples (AD: air-dried, AD_PM: air-dried plasma-modified, L: lyophilized, L_PM: lyophilized plasma-modified). Kruskal–Wallis One Way Analysis of Variance on Ranks, Dunn’s method. The box plot black central line shows the median; its outer edges represent the 1st and 3rd quartile (Q1 is the 25th percentile, Q3 is the 75th percentile of the sample), and the whiskers depict the maximum and minimum values. Statistically significant differences among the experimental groups ($p \leq 0.05$) are indicated above the columns by Roman numerals of differing groups (all: significantly different in comparison with all other groups). For each experimental group of samples and for each parameter, 9–26 measurements for NHDFs and 8–17 measurements for HUVECs were performed.

necessary for tissue engineering, can be facilitated by mechanical reinforcement of the BNC, e.g. with gelatin (Bao et al., 2022) or xyloglucan, especially when bearing RGD oligopeptides, i.e. ligands for integrin adhesion receptors on cells (Fink et al., 2011). In this context, it should be emphasized that not only blending or chemical methods, such as fixation or crosslinking, can be used to combine BNC with other biomolecules. Physical modifications, namely the PM used in our study, also represent an excellent tool for grafting biomolecules by means of radicals formed in the polymer chains by their partial degradation. This grafting technique was advantageously used in our earlier study performed on plasma-modified polylactide in order to further enhance its attractiveness for the adhesion, growth and differentiation of mesenchymal stem cells (Travnickova et al., 2021).

Plasma modification may also have a sterilising effect on BNC, which itself has no antimicrobial effect (for a review, see Bacakova et al., 2019). Non-thermal plasma is a promising tool for sterilization of various biomaterials designed for implantation into the human body, such as polymers and metals (Maillet et al., 2023), for various animal products, such as milk or meat, or even for directly killing bacteria in wounds or in the oral cavity for dentistry purposes (for a review, see Yang et al., 2023). A direct antimicrobial effect of BNC can be achieved by combining it with various agents, such as chitosan, curcumin

(Zikmundova et al., 2020), antibiotics or metal-based nanoparticles containing Ag, Au, Ti, Cu, Zn or iron oxide (Nosrati et al., 2021; 2023).

The presented results for the cell numbers were in line with the morphology of the cells on the studied materials (Fig. 8). Microscopic images revealed that NHDFs were more numerous and were spread over a larger area on the BNC_PM samples than on the unmodified samples. This was especially apparent on BNC_L. Unmodified BNC_L contained only sparse cells, while on BNC_L_PM, the cells were subconfluent, similarly as on the control PS dishes. In contrast, HUVECs were more numerous and more widely spread on BNC_AD than on BNC_L, particularly on BNC_L_PM.

On the 6th day of cultivation, the number of viable cells was estimated indirectly by a metabolic test, based on the reduction of oxidized non-fluorescent blue resazurin into a red fluorescent dye resorufin by the mitochondrial respiratory chain in live cells (Fig. 9). The reason was that the cells, at least on some samples, were confluent and often overlapping each other (Fig. 10), which disabled direct cell counting.

The intensity of the fluorescence of resorufin indicated that both cell types, i.e. NHDFs and HUVECs, significantly preferred BNC_PM membranes for their growth. At the same time, the cells also preferred BNC_AD to BNC_L samples. As a result, the highest metabolic activity of NHDFs and HUVECs was detected on the BNC_AD_PM samples, while the

Fig. 8. Morphology of normal human dermal fibroblasts (NHDF) and human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVEC) on day 3 after seeding on BNC samples (AD: air-dried, AD_PM: air-dried plasma-modified, L: lyophilized, L_PM: lyophilized plasma-modified) and in the control polystyrene (PS) wells. The cells were stained with a LIVE/DEAD kit. Viable cells are colored green, dead cells are red. Olympus IX 51 epifluorescence microscope, DP 70 digital camera, objective 4 ×, eyepiece 10 × (total magnification of the optical system 40 ×), scale bar 200 μm.

lowest values were measured on BNC_L, which was apparent especially in HUVECs (only approx. one third of the value on the control PS). On BNC_AD_PM, the metabolic activity of the NHDFs approached the value on the control PS, and in HUVECs this activity even significantly exceeded (approx. by 46 %) the control value (Fig. 9).

Microscopic images (Fig. 10) revealed that on day 6 after seeding, the NHDFs on BNC_AD_PM were fully confluent, similarly as on the control PS. HUVECs even reached confluence on both BNC_AD and BNC_AD_PM, while both cell types were rather subconfluent and non-homogeneously distributed on BNC_L and on BNC_L_PM. This can be attributed to the higher porosity of the lyophilized samples, which led to greater heterogeneity of their surface, greater swelling and insufficient mechanical support for growing cells. Similar results were obtained in our earlier study performed on BNC seeded with human epidermal HaCaT

keratinocytes. The initial adhesion of these cells was higher on BNC_L, while their subsequent growth and their final population density were higher on BC_AD, and were further improved by PM (Kutová et al., 2021). In another study, performed on cellulose/collagen composites, a composite with a lower swelling capacity, i.e. containing oxidized cellulose, also provided more suitable support for colonization with human adipose tissue-derived stem cells than the composite containing carboxymethylcellulose with a higher degree of swelling and lower mechanical strength (Kacvinská et al., 2022).

3.6. Gene expression of markers of cell adhesion and phenotypic maturation

The markers of adhesion and phenotypic maturation of cells on BNC

Fig. 9. Resazurin metabolic test of normal human dermal fibroblasts (NHDF) and human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVEC) and on day 6 after seeding in the control polystyrene (PS) wells or on BNC samples (AD: air-dried, AD_PM: air-dried plasma-modified, L: lyophilized, L_PM: lyophilized plasma-modified). Mean \pm S.E. M. from three measurements for each cell type and experimental group of samples. One way ANOVA, Student-Newman-Keuls Method. Statistically significant differences among the experimental groups ($p \leq 0.05$) are indicated above the columns by Roman numerals of differing groups (all: significantly different in comparison with all other groups).

samples were evaluated at the gene expression level (i.e. at mRNA level) by the real-time PCR method on day 6 after cell seeding.

Talin and vinculin were chosen as markers of cell adhesion. At protein level, these molecules are structural components of focal adhesion plaques, associated with the cell adhesion receptors and connecting these receptors with the actin cytoskeleton. Talin and vinculin, also called molecules of “the cell membrane cytoskeleton”, participate in the transmission of mechanical signals from the surrounding environment into the cell. Talin has been reported to participate in cell-matrix adhesion, while vinculin was found in both cell-matrix and cell-cell contacts (for a review, see [Bacakova et al., 2011](#)).

In NHDFs, the gene expression of talin and vinculin was markedly higher on both types of BNC membranes unmodified with plasma than on the control PS and on the PM membranes. The expression fold change in comparison with PS was highest in the cells on plasma-unmodified BNC_L. However, on PM membranes, the expression was generally similar to that on the control PS, except in the case of BNC_L_PM, where it was increased, but much less than on BNC_L ([Fig. 11A, B](#)). In other words, the expression of talin and vinculin was similar to the control value in those BNC samples on which NHDFs showed the highest metabolic activity, viability and the highest degree of confluence (*cf.* [Figs. 11 and 9](#)). These samples were plasma-modified (similar to tissue culture PS), and such samples are known to support the adsorption of cell adhesion-mediating proteins from the serum supplement of the culture medium. These proteins then stimulate the binding of cell adhesion receptors, their assembly into focal adhesion plaques, and the synthesis of associated talin and vinculin proteins, which can then suppress the expression of talin and vinculin at mRNA level through negative feedback.

A similar trend was also observed in the expression of the THY1 gene encoding the CD90 receptor, i.e. a glycoprotein adhesion molecule of the immunoglobulin superfamily, playing a role in cell-matrix and cell-cell interactions, and considered as a marker of fibroblasts. The expression of THY1 in NHDFs on untreated BNC exceeded the value on the control PS and on both BNC_PM membranes, being highest in cells cultured on BNC_L. At the same time, the expression of THY1 in cells cultured on both BNC_PM membranes was similar or even slightly lower in comparison with the control value on PS ([Fig. 11C](#)). The explanation could be similar as for talin and vinculin – the cells on the PM samples reached

confluence earlier, which was associated with earlier termination of the transcription of genes for cell adhesion molecules, initiation of the translation process and the formation of cell-matrix and cell-cell adhesion structures, and then their negative feedback to mRNA expression ([Lodish et al., 1999](#)). Similarly, in our earlier study performed on human osteoblast-like cells grown on nanofibrous polymeric meshes reinforced with diamond nanoparticles, the expression of adhesion and differentiation markers at mRNA level showed a tendency to decrease with increasing expression of these markers at protein level ([Stankova et al., 2019](#)).

In HUVECs, the gene expression level of vinculin was significantly lower in cells cultured on all tested BNC scaffolds in comparison with cells on the control PS, and this result was particularly noticeable on BNC_AD ([Fig. 12A](#)). BNC_AD and BNC_AD_PM were, together with PS, the only samples on which HUVECs were able to form a confluent cell layer on day 6 after seeding. In addition, on day 6, the metabolic activity (considered to be an indirect marker of cell number) of HUVECs on BNC_AD_PM was even significantly higher than on PS. Thus, a similar explanation can be used for HUVECs as for NHDFs: the expression of vinculin at mRNA level was silenced in favor of translation, proteosynthesis and the formation of specific protein-based adhesion structures ([Lodish et al., 1999](#)).

However, the expression of mRNA for vinculin was also low in HUVECs on the BNC_L and BNC_L_PM samples, on which these cells grew non-homogeneously and were not able to form a confluent layer on day 6. These samples, especially BNC_L_PM, proved to be relatively poor substrates for the growth, viability and metabolic activity of HUVECs from day 1 to day 6 of cultivation, and these substrates were perhaps also unable to stimulate the gene expression of molecules involved in cell adhesion.

The gene expression of PECAM-1 (CD31) showed almost the same trend as the expression of vinculin ([Fig. 12B](#)), and the explanation for this result could also be similar to the case of vinculin. PECAM-1 is a highly glycosylated protein of the immunoglobulin superfamily, considered as a marker of endothelial cells, although it is also expressed in other cells within the vascular compartment, such as leukocytes, lymphocytes, macrophages and platelets ([Woodfin et al., 2007](#)). In endothelial cells, PECAM-1 is localized preferentially in junctions between adjacent cells, and this adhesion molecule can therefore be

Fig. 10. Normal human dermal fibroblasts (NHDFs) and human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVECs) on day 6 after seeding on BNC samples (AD: air-dried, AD_PM: air-dried plasma-modified, L: lyophilized, L_PM: lyophilized plasma-modified), and in the control polystyrene (PS) wells. The cells were stained with a LIVE/DEAD kit. Viable cells are colored green, dead cells are red. Olympus IX 51 epifluorescence microscope, DP 70 digital camera, objective 4 ×, eyepiece 10 × (total magnification of the optical system 40 ×), scale bar 200 μm.

considered as a marker of the integrity of the endothelial cell layer.

However, the expression of the KDR gene that encodes vascular endothelial growth factor receptor 2 (VEGFR2), a typical marker of endothelial cell phenotype, was significantly increased in HUVECs cultured on all tested BNC samples in comparison with the control cells on PS (Fig. 12C). At the same time, this expression was significantly higher on BNC_PM than on unmodified BNC, and also significantly higher on BNC_L than on BNC_AD. VEGFR2 binds VEGF, i.e. a factor important for the survival, migration and proliferation of endothelial cells (Wang et al., 2020). It can therefore be supposed that HUVECs tried by increased expression of VEGFR2 to overcome certain unfavorable conditions for their adhesion and growth. However, VEGF also promotes tubulogenesis in endothelial cells and vasculogenesis, which can take place advantageously in porous matrices represented by lyophilized

BNC, and should be further investigated.

4. Conclusion and further perspectives

We prepared air-dried or lyophilized bacterial nanocellulose (BNC), either unmodified or modified by plasma, in order to increase its attractiveness for cell colonization. Plasma modification of BNC had a positive influence on the initial adhesion and the subsequent growth of normal human dermal fibroblasts (NHDFs). However, in HUVECs, this positive effect was apparent only on day 6 of cultivation, when the cells on the plasma-modified samples showed higher metabolic activity than the cells on unmodified samples. Moreover, in HUVECs, the effect of plasma-modification of lyophilized BNC was even negative, i.e. decreasing the size of the cell spreading area (day 1) or cell viability (day

Fig. 11. Gene expression of talin (*TLN1*), vinculin (*VCL*) and CD90 (*THY1*) in normal human dermal fibroblasts on day 6 after seeding on BNC (AD: air-dried, AD_PM: air-dried plasma-modified, L: lyophilized, L_PM: lyophilized plasma modified). The graphs compare the gene expression fold change normalized to the expression data acquired on the control polystyrene, which was used as a calibrator (value set to zero in the graphs). Mean \pm S.D. from three measurements for each gene and experimental group of samples. One way ANOVA, Holm-Sidak Method. Statistically significant differences among the experimental groups ($p < 0.01$) are indicated above the columns by Roman numerals of differing groups (all: significantly different in comparison with all other groups).

Fig. 12. Gene expression of vinculin (*VCL*), CD31 (*PECAM1*) and VEGFR2 (*KDR*) in human umbilical vein endothelial cells on day 6 after seeding (AD: air-dried, AD_PM: air-dried plasma-modified, L: lyophilized, L_PM: lyophilized plasma modified). The graphs compare the gene expression fold change normalized to the expression data acquired on the control polystyrene, which was used as a calibrator (value set to zero in the graphs). Mean \pm S.D. from three measurements for each gene and experimental group of samples. One way ANOVA, Holm-Sidak Method. Statistically significant differences among the experimental groups ($p < 0.01$) are indicated above the columns by Roman numerals of differing groups (all: significantly different in comparison with all other groups).

3). On lyophilized BNC, HUVECs were not able to form a confluent cell layer and were distributed non-homogeneously. An explanation could be a relative mechanical weakness of lyophilized BNC, due to its porous structure and high swelling capacity, which was further enhanced by plasma modification. In NHDFs, the expression of mRNA for markers of cell adhesion and phenotypic maturation (talin, vinculin, CD90) on plasma-modified samples was similar to that on the control polystyrene, while in HUVECs, this expression was either lower (vinculin, CD31) or higher (VEGFR2) than on the control polystyrene. It can be concluded that plasma-modification of BNC represents a promising tool for creating suitable cell carriers for wound healing (e.g. air-dried BNC for cell delivery, especially in the form of cell sheets) or for tissue engineering (e.g. porous lyophilized BNC for creating vascularized skin constructs). However, cell type-specific differences in the response to various material modifications should be taken into account, i.e. the resulting material properties must be tailored to meet the requirements of the cell types needed for the given application.

Data availability

The data presented in this study are available at 10.5281/zenodo.10497424, and are also available on request from the corresponding author.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Lubica Staňková: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Supervision. **Anna Kutová:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Martina Doubková:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Ondřej Kvítek:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Barbora Vokatá:** Methodology, Data curation. **Antonín Sedlár:** Visualization. **Hazem Idriss:** Investigation, Visualization. **Petr Slepíčka:** Validation, Supervision. **Václav Švorčík:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition, Project administration. **Lucie Bačáková:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition, Project administration.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper. One of the authors (Lucie Bacakova) is a Guest Editor for *Cells* (MDPI) and was not involved in the editorial review or the decision to publish this article.

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